

Complex networks allow a quantitative analysis of historical networks by data mining the Wikipedia corpus

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The development of revolutionary ideas, cultural breakthroughs, or paradigm shifts typically emerges from complex interactions among many people, concepts, and objects that structure social, historical, and cultural spaces. These interactions are difficult to quantify, and the increasing number of cultural elements to be considered would eventually make it hard, if not impossible, to fully understand the cultural dynamics using traditional tools. To overcome these limitations, several quantitative methodologies have been proposed recently (Schich et al., 2014; Goldfarb et al., 2015; Brown et al., 2017), some of them using Wikipedia as a suitable source for data mining and quantitative cultural research. Based on the formalism of complex networks theory, it has been recently shown that it is possible to convert the network of internal links on Wikipedia into a meaningful network of knowledge (Schwartz, 2021). Using this methodology, it has been possible to quantitatively analyse the cultural network that relates Pablo Picasso, Albert Einstein and James Joyce. This approach has been shown to successfully address a multiscale analysis that allows characterising individual nodes (degree and betweenness centrality, participation coefficient), clusters (size, density, openness) and the whole network (modularity, assortativity matrix). The same approach has also been applied to study the interactions among Michelangelo, Copernicus, and Pico della Mirandola in the Italian Renaissance (Miccio et al., 2022).

It is worth noticing that in these cases, we were studying the corresponding historical networks as represented on Wikipedia. Although this could represent a partial and biased view of history, the agreement between the results obtained using this methodology and the well-established historical knowledge makes this approach suitable for this kind of study. For the purpose of this research, the important point is how

people, ideas, and objects are related among them. Thus, the content of the Wikipedia articles is not relevant for the present study; only the links to other articles are significant. Moreover, the metrics we use to determine the relatedness between two articles are based on many links (hundreds or even thousands in some cases), making this method robust against noise and biases. We have shown in previous studies that the simple observation of what is connected to what, properly treated, can unveil relevant knowledge about the structure of cultural networks.

The success of this methodology applied to specific events (Schwartz, 2021; Miccio et al., 2022) encourages us to move from particular cases to characterising an entire historical period. Thus, the present work aims to quantitatively analyse a given historical period's cultural network (as represented on Wikipedia). In particular, we will focus on the interdisciplinary cultural network that connects art, science, and philosophy in the seventeenth century. This period is somehow in between the historical ages analysed in our previous works, allowing a direct comparison to prior results. Instead of focusing on specific cases (i.e., Johannes Vermeer, Christiaan Huygens and Blaise Pascal – see Figure), we propose a statistical approach by taking many triads to determine the average properties of the period. In this way, we can understand the flow of knowledge among different disciplines and quantify the individual behaviour of nodes and the collective characteristics of clusters and networks.

To achieve this challenge, we used the normalised Google distance to measure the structural relatedness between each pair of Wikipedia entries. Based on these metrics, we generated 465 undirected networks representing cultural maps of the Wikipedia articles related to the studied historical period. Averaging this set of networks allows us to perform a multiscale analysis to understand the global, cluster and individual behaviours. Thus, we found that the average normalised modularity is 0.862, higher than the value we obtained for the Italian Renaissance (0.77) and lower than that we observed at the beginning of the 20th century (0.88). This progressive increment of modularity agrees with the well-known rise of the disciplinary specialisation in the last centuries. The detailed analysis of the inter-cluster interactions reveals a power law distribution of the links, whereas a lognormal distribution is observed for the intra-cluster connections. At the level of individual nodes, the participation coefficient allows us to determine the most relevant agents for the studied period and to understand how the knowledge is shared among different disciplines. This approach allows a qualitative as well as a quantitative analysis of cultural networks, making appropriate use of visualization tools and mathematical calculations.

Thus, by combining ideas borrowed from knowledge discovery in databases and complex networks theory, the approach proposed here reveals the emergence of collective dynamics and finds subtle connections between elements (people, ideas, or works) present on Wikipedia. It is important to emphasize here that this approach is not limited to the use of the Wikipedia corpus. The use of artificial intelligence allows extending the results presented here to any database, provided it contains enough information. Hence, this approach provides new insights into the structure of cultural networks, reveals unknown characteristics of the different disciplines, and boosts quantitative studies in history and cultural dynamics.

References

- Brown, D.M., A. Soto-Corominas, and J.L. Suárez. “The Preliminaries Project: Geography, Networks, and Publication in the Spanish Golden Age.” *Digit. Scholarsh. Humanit* 32 (2017) 709–732.
- Goldfarb, D., D. Merkl, and M. Schich. “Quantifying Cultural Histories via Person Networks in Wikipedia.” *arXiv* (2015) doi:10.48550/arXiv.1506.06580.
- Miccio, Luis A., Carlos Gámez-Pérez, Juan Kuis Suárez, and Gustavo A. Schwartz. “Mapping the Networked Context of Copernicus, Michelangelo, and della Mirandola in Wikipedia.” *Advances in Complex Systems* 25 (2022) 2240010.
- Schich, M., C. Song, Y.-Y. Ahn, A. Mirsky, M. Martino, A.-L. Barabási, and D. A. Helbing. “Network Framework of Cultural History.” *Science* 345 (2014) 558–562.
- Schwartz, Gustavo A. “Complex networks reveal emergent interdisciplinary knowledge in Wikipedia.” *Humanities & Social Sciences Communications* 8 (2021) 127.